

Basic Education as Enabler for Sustainable National Development in Biase Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria

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Abstract

This study examined basic education as an enabler for sustainable national development in Biase Local Government Area of Cross River State. The study adopted a descriptive survey design. Two research questions were formulated and answered in the study. The population was made up of eight hundred and thirty (830) respondents, (380 JSSI 1-3 and 450 primary 1-6) teachers. The sample of the study is made up of eighty-three (83) teachers which represent 10 per cent of the population selected using a proportionate stratified sampling technique. The instrument was a 4-point rating scale weighted as Strongly Agree (SA) - 4 points, Agree (A) - 3 points, Disagree (D) - 2 point, Strongly Disagree (SD) - 1 point. A structured questionnaire was developed for data collection. The instrument was distributed and data obtained were analysed using mean and standard deviation while the two null hypotheses were analysed using a one-sample t-test at the 0.05 level of significance. It was found out that Child's accessibility and adult accessibility to basic education influence sustainable national development. Hence, it is recommended among others that Federal Government should ensure that Children have access to basic education to foster sustainable national development.

Keywords: Basic, education, sustainable, national development.

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Introduction

Education is a crucial sector in any nation. Being a major investment in human capital development, it plays a critical role in long-term productivity and growth at both micro and macro levels. Education is an instrument for national development, to this end, the formulation of ideas, their integration for national development, and the interaction of persons and ideas are all aspects of education. Therefore, every Nigerian child shall have a right to equal educational opportunities irrespective of any real or imagined disabilities each according to his or her ability, (NPE,2014). Education is a transfer of knowledge from one generation to another; it is a system or practice of teaching and learning. Also in its broadest meaning, education is any process by which an individual gains knowledge or insight, or develops attitude or skill. It is the process of facilitating learning, or the acquisition of knowledge, skills, values, beliefs, and habits. Education frequently takes place under the guidance of educators, but learners may also

educate themselves. "Education in its' largest sense is any act or experience that has a formative effect in the mind, character or physical ability of an individual. In its technical sense, education is a process by which society deliberately transmits its accumulated knowledge, skills and values from one generation to another, (Ejeh 2017). Education in Nigeria continues to be our national discourse at all levels especially basic education.

Basic education simply put by Nigerian National policy on education (2014) shall be of 9-year duration, comprising 6 years of primary education and 3 years of junior secondary education. It shall be free and compulsory. It shall also include adult and non-formal education programmes at primary and junior secondary education levels for the adults and out-of-school youths. The primary school years and early first three years in Junior Secondary school that form the 9-year Basic Education are very important in a child's intellectual, moral and all-around development of a child. National Council on Education (NCE) in conjunction with the Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC) thought it wise to come up with the revised 9-year Basic Education Curriculum and teachers guide that centred towards meeting the needs of children within the school-going age to achieve sustainability in our education system, (NERDC, 2013).

Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council (NERDC) propounded the school curriculum and they have developed a high-quality 9-year Basic Educational curriculum. This new school curriculum was approved by the National Council of Education since 2007. NERDC curriculum at a glanced, 2013 further states that the curriculum emphasizes functional numeracy, literacy, and technological and productive life-skill. It also provides ICT as well as entrepreneurial skills. Every learner who has gone through the 9 years of basic education should have acquired appropriate levels of literacy, numeracy, manipulative, communicative and life-long, learning, as a basis for scientific and reflective thinking. New 9-Year Basic Education Curriculum according to Obioma (2012), was developed for the attainment of Education for All (EFA) goals, the critical targets of the National Economic Empowerment and Development Strategies (NEEDS) and the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs), This curriculum has the following subjects: Mathematics, English, history, Basic Science and Technology and Social Studies as core subjects in the Primary Schools. Other subjects are Christian Religion Studies, Islamic Studies, national values, and Home Economics. The philosophy of the 9-year Basic Education is that at the end of the basic education the students should have acquired appropriate levels of literacy, numeracy, manipulative, communicative and life-skills as well as the ethical, moral and civic values required for laying a solid foundation for life-long learning as a basis for scientific and reflective thinking, (NERDC, 2017)

Therefore, Basic Education has remained an instrument of change and national development. It is a social process and the medium for the acquisition of relevant knowledge, skills and attitudes for national development. Nations desire closer cooperation, improvement in the quality of life, respect for the rule of law and Human Rights and a peaceful co-existence among communities, schools and nations constitute global issues of concern. Basic education in Nigeria constitutes a vital tool for addressing virtually all national developmental problems. Education is not only an end in itself but it is a key instrument for bringing about changes in

knowledge, values, behaviours and lifestyles required to achieve sustainability and stability within and among countries (Abubakar in Ejeh,2017).

Sustainable Development is a process of improving the range of opportunities that will enable individual humans and communities to achieve their aspirations and full potential over a sustained period while maintaining the resilience of economic, social and environmental systems Munasinghe in (Ejeh & Odiagbe, 2017). Also, sustainable development is a construct, which envisions development as meeting the need of the present generation without compromising the needs of the future generation Ugoh in (Ejeh & Odiagbe, 2017). They argued that sustainable development is only possible or assured when it is agreed and indeed concrete steps are taken to raise the level of literacy and numeracy in any society.

Human development is an essential component of the social, economic and political development of society, for it guarantees a happy and secured life. To be able to attain effective human development to ensure sustainable development, knowledge and skills imparted by formal education holds key since it provides the basis for the fight against illiteracy. One effective way of promoting this is through basic education because knowledge acquired by students at this stage has a long-lasting effect and reduces the ills associated with social vices from those who were not exposed to basic education. (Uwabunkeonye, 2017). Sustainable Development Goals is an agenda to end poverty, promote prosperity and help people's wellbeing while protecting the planet by the year 2030. The united nation led up a working group made up of country representatives and experts on education, health and other subjects. They look at the most pressing problems faced by people across the world and the issues that prevent their lives improvement. Basic education is the key to Sustainable Development Goals. www.aworldatshool.org/.

The Sustainable Development Goals, otherwise known as the Global Goals, build on the Millennium Development Goals (MDGs) eight anti-poverty targets that the world is committed to achieving. The MDGs, adopted in 2000, aimed at an array of issues that included slashing poverty, hunger, disease, and access to water and sanitation. The new global target for improving people's lives around the world, the Sustainable Development Goals, do much more than just extend to another 15 years the remit of the Millennium Development Goals. The Sustainable Development Goals agenda, an unprecedented push to tackle the causes of poverty, looks at the big picture. It embraces the need for economic development that leaves no one behind and gives every child a fair chance of living a decent life. And it faces squarely our duty to protect future generations by limiting climate change, adopting renewable energy and managing resources sustainably (Africa Progress Panel 2006).

Basic education and sustainable national development are interwoven and interrelated. While national development is targeted towards producing or creating something new or more advanced for the society and its members. Basic education is a tool that can enhance the desired sustainable development. Therefore, basic education and sustainable national development are a two-sided coin. The fact that education and sustainable development shows glaring

connectivity probably explained why scholars emphasized the need for education to achieve the desired sustainable development.

Statement of problem

Basic education is for a 9-year duration. That comprises six (6) years of primary education, and three (3) years of junior secondary education and ought to be free and compulsory as enshrined in the national policy on education. To achieve the objective of basic education in our educational system, the federal government through the Nigerian Educational Research and Development Council has developed a high-quality 9-year Basic Educational curriculum which ought to be implemented but unfortunately, the aims and objectives of basic education are still not yet achieved. This can be seen in the high school fees charged by some states in Nigeria that have made the programme not accessible to the majority. Despite the effort made by the Federal Government to ensure free and compulsory education still, the problem persists, Given the above premise, the question which this study seeks to answer is: to what extent is basic education an enabler for sustainable national development in Biase Local Government Area of Cross River State, Nigeria.

Purpose of the study

The purpose of this study is to ascertain if basic education is an enabler for sustainable national development in Biase local government area of Cross River, Nigeria. Specifically, this study seeks to investigate:

1. The extent to which Child's accessibility to basic education influences sustainable national development.
2. The extent to which adult accessibility to basic education influences sustainable national development.

Research questions

The following research questions are put forward to direct this study:

1. To what does child's accessibility to basic education influence sustainable national development?
2. To what extent does adult accessibility to basic education influence sustainable national development?

Hypotheses

Two null hypotheses were tested at the .05 level of significance.

1. There is no significant difference between Child's accessibility to basic education and sustainable national development?
 2. There is no significant difference between adult accessibility to basic education and sustainable national development?
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Methods

The design of this study was a descriptive survey. This design was appropriate as the study aimed to get information on the extent to which basic education is an enabler for sustainable national development in Biase local government area of Cross River, Nigeria. There are 24 primary schools and 17 secondary schools owned by the government in Biase local government area. **Source:** Baise Local Government Education Authority, Calabar (August 2020). The population of this study comprises primary 1-6 and JSS1-3 of the pupils and students in public schools in Biase L.G.A of Cross River State. The sample for this study were eighty-three (83) respondents which represent 10 per cent of the population, thirty-eight (38) Jss1-3 teachers and forty-five (45) primary1-6 teachers from the area of study using a proportionate stratified random sampling technique. A questionnaire was used as an instrument for data collection in the study. The questionnaire entitled, "Basic Education as Enabler for Sustainable National Development Questionnaire, (BEESNDQ) was developed by the researcher. The instrument was designed to collect information on how basic education influences sustainable national development in the Biase local government area of Cross River, Nigeria.

The instrument has ten (10) items and is divided into 2 sections. Section A seeks information on the personal data of the respondents. Section 2 has 2 clusters; Cluster 1 seeks to investigate the extent to which a Child's accessibility to basic education influences sustainable national development and this cluster has five (5) items. Cluster 2 of the instrument has five (5) items and elicits information on the extent to which adult accessibility to basic education influences sustainable national development. The instruments were designed on a four-point rating scale weighted as follows: Clusters 1 and 2 use the following response mode: Strongly Agree (SA) - 4 points, Agree (A)- 3 points, Disagree (D) -2 point, Strongly Disagree (SD) -1 point. The questionnaire was administered by the researcher with the assistance of two research assistants. These research assistants were trained on the method of administering and retrieving the instruments. Direct delivery and retrieval system was used. This helped the researcher to recover all the instruments from the respondents. The data were analysed using mean (X) score and Standard Deviation (SD) in answering the two research questions posed for the study. The mean score above 2.50 is an indication of agreement while below 2.50 is a disagreement with the item. One sample t-test statistics was used to test hypotheses 1 and 2 at 0.5 level of significance.

Results

For the Child's accessibility to basic education, adult accessibility to basic education to have significant differences in sustainable national development, the score on each variable should be significantly greater than 12.5 (which is the midpoint between, which is 2.5 multiply by 5 the number of items measuring each variable). This hypothesis was tested with a test of one sample mean (population t-test). The result is presented in Table 1. The entries in Table 1 show the means, standard deviations and t-values for the extent Child's accessibility to basic

education, adult accessibility to basic education influence sustainable national development. From the Table, it can be observed that the mean score for Child's accessibility to basic education (3.142) with standard deviation (1.456), the t-calculated value of (19.773) and the mean score for adult accessibility to basic education (2.945) with standard deviation (1.032), the t-calculated value of (26.016) are each higher than the hypothesized reference value of 12.50 ($t=1.664$; $p < .05$). With this result, the null hypothesis was rejected. The alternative hypotheses were accepted. This implies that there is a significant difference between Child's accessibility to basic education, adult accessibility to basic education and sustainable national development.

Table 1: Population t-test analysis of the significant difference between Child's accessibility to basic education, adult accessibility to basic education and sustainable national development (N=83)

Sub-variables	Sample mean	Mean error	SD	df	t-value	p
Child accessibility	3.142	0.159	1.456	82	19.773	.000
Adult accessibility	2.945	0.1132	1.032	82	26.016	.001

$p < 0.05$; t -critical = 1.664; Reference mean = 12.50

Conclusion

From the result of the study, it could be concluded that Child's accessibility and adult accessibility to basic education influence sustainable national development. This result also concluded that there is a significant difference between Child's accessibility and adult accessibility to basic education and sustainable national development.

Recommendations

Data collected from this study has been interpreted and the result discussed. Based on the discussion, the following recommendations were made:

1. Federal Government should ensure that Children have access to basic education to foster sustainable national development.
2. The Universal Basic Education Commission should work closely with State Universal Basic Education Boards and Local Government Education Authorities to facilitate the accessibility of basic education in sustainable national development.

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